

A STUDY ON TEACHER COMPETENCY AND TEACHER BURNOUT AT HIGHER SECONDARY LEVEL

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Abstract:

In this study, an attempt has been made to study the teacher competency and teacher burnout at higher secondary level. The Teacher Competency Rating Scale (TCRS) constructed and validated by the investigator (2019) and Teacher Burnout Rating Scale (TBRS) constructed and validated by Sathiyagirirajan (2002) were used to collect the data from a sample of 302 higher secondary teachers working in Cuddalore District of Tamilnadu, India. The survey method has been followed and random sampling technique was used in administration of the research tools. The result of the analysis reveals that the higher secondary teachers are having average competency and burnout. It is found that higher secondary teachers do not differ significantly in teacher competency in respect of gender and educational qualification. It is found that higher secondary teachers do not differ significantly in teacher burnout in respect of Gender and they differ significantly in teacher burnout in respect of educational qualification. It is found that there is no significant relationship between the teacher competency of higher secondary school teachers and their burnout.

Introduction:

Competencies refer to skills or knowledge that lead to superior performance. These are formed through an individual/organization's knowledge, skills and abilities and provide a framework for distinguishing between poor performances through to exceptional performance. Competencies can apply at organizational, individual, team, and occupational and functional levels. Competencies are individual abilities or characteristics that are key to effectiveness in work.

Burnout is a prolonged response to chronic emotional and interpersonal stressors on the job, and is defined by the three dimensions of exhaustion, cynicism, and inefficacy. The past 25 years of research has established the complexity of the construct, and places the individual stress experience within a larger organizational context of people's relation to their work. Recently, the work on burnout has expanded internationally and has led to new conceptual models.

Need and Importance of the Study:

Competencies refer to skills or knowledge that lead to superior performance. These are formed through an individual/organization's knowledge, skills and abilities and provide a framework for distinguishing between poor performances through to exceptional performance. Competencies can apply at organizational, individual, team, and occupational and functional levels. Competencies are individual abilities or characteristics that are key to effectiveness in work. Competency is meant for the skills, knowledge, value, etc. which a teacher process and they are the tools of teaching. Only the teacher who processes all the skills, knowledge and values can function effectively in an academic situation and is said to be competent to teach in any particular situation. Job burnout is a problem in many professions, but it significantly more prevalent in the helping professions. Teachers, as well as administrators, counsellors, doctors, nurses, police officers, and soon have the additional burden of extreme responsibility for the well being of others on top of the multitude of stressors that stem from routine job activities.

Operational Definitions of the Terms:

Teacher Competency:

Competence includes knowledge, skills, attitudes and experiences, which has to be target category of profession of teacher. Ability to perform or carry out defined tasks in a particular context, at a high level of excellence.

Teacher Burnout:

Burnout is defined as a state of physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion caused by long-term involvement in situations that are emotionally demanding.

Higher Secondary Teacher:

The teachers who were teaching 11th and 12th standard students.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the teacher competency of higher secondary school teachers.
- To study the teacher burnout of higher secondary school teachers.

- The significant difference, if any, between a) gender and b) educational qualification of the higher secondary school teachers in respect of their teacher competency.
- The significant difference, if any, between a) gender and b) educational qualification of the higher secondary school teachers in respect of their teacher burnout.
- The nature of the relationship between the teacher competency of higher secondary school teachers and their burnout.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- The level of teacher competency of higher secondary teacher is average.
- The level of teacher burnout of higher secondary teacher is average.
- There is no significant difference, if any, between a) gender and b) educational qualification of the higher secondary school teachers in respect of their teacher competency.
- There is no significant difference, if any, between a) gender and b) educational qualification of the higher secondary school teachers in respect of their teacher burnout.
- There is no significant relationship between the teacher competency of higher secondary school teachers and their burnout.

Method of the Study:

Normative survey method has been employed in the present study.

Sample of the Study:

Random sampling technique was used in the selection of as many as 302 higher secondary school teachers in Cuddalore district of Tamil Nadu.

Scoring Procedure:

Teacher Competency Rating Scale (TCRS) constructed and validated by the investigator (2019). The scale consists of 45 statements and the five alternative responses. The maximum marks is 225 and the minimum mark is 45.

The Burnout rating scale was prepared by Sathiyagirirajan. S, (2002). This scale consists of 40 statements. The responses were given as A, B, C, D and E on a five point scale ranging from 4,3,2,1 and 0. The Maximum score for this scale is 160 and the minimum mark is 0.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

Descriptive Analysis:

Hypothesis 1: The level of teacher competency of higher secondary teacher is average.

Table 1: Showing the Mean and Standard Deviation scores of Teacher Competency of Higher Secondary Teachers

Variable	N	M	SD
Teacher Competency	302	123.08	18.30

It is evident from the Table 1, that the calculated mean score is found to be 123.08 and the standard deviation value is 18.30. Therefore hypothesis 1 is accepted and it is concluded that higher secondary teachers are having average competency.

Hypothesis 2: The level of teacher burnout of higher secondary teacher is average.

Table 1: Showing the Mean and Standard Deviation scores of Teacher Burnout of Higher Secondary Teachers

Variable	N	M	SD
Teacher Burnout	302	76.71	16.01

It is evident from the Table 1, that the calculated mean score is found to be 76.71 and the standard deviation value is 16.01. Therefore hypothesis 1 is accepted and it is concluded that higher secondary teachers are having average burnout.

Differential Analysis:

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference, if any, between a) gender and b) educational qualification of the higher secondary school teachers in respect of their teacher competency.

Table 3: Showing the ‘t’ Value for Teacher Competency Scores of Higher Secondary teachers in respect of the Sub-Samples

Variable	Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Teacher Competence	Male	123	122.15	17.26	1.60	Not Significant
	Female	179	123.21	16.84		
	UG	170	120.81	16.45	0.96	Not Significant
	PG	132	121.14	16.68		

It is evident from the Table 3, that the calculated ‘t’ values is found to be 1.60 and 0.96 which are not significant. Hence, the framed null hypothesis 3(a) and 3(b) is accepted and it is concluded that the higher secondary teachers do not differ significantly in teacher competency in respect of gender and educational qualification.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference, if any, between a) gender and b) educational qualification of the higher secondary school teachers in respect of their teacher burnout.

Table 4: Showing the ‘t’ Value for Teacher Burnout Scores of Higher Secondary teachers in respect of the Sub-Samples

Variable	Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Teacher Burnout	Male	123	78.19	17.42	0.12	Not Significant
	Female	179	78.28	17.24		
	UG	170	80.88	16.49	2.84	Significant
	PG	132	76.48	17.66		

It is evident from the Table 4, that the calculated ‘t’ value is found to be 0.12 which is not significant. Hence, the framed null hypothesis 4(a) is accepted and it is concluded that the higher secondary students do not differ significantly in teacher burnout in respect of gender.

The calculated ‘t’ value is found to be 2.84 which is significant. Hence, the framed null hypothesis 4(b) is rejected and it is concluded that the higher secondary students differ significantly in teacher burnout in respect of educational qualification.

Correlation Analysis:

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between the teacher competency of higher secondary school teachers and their burnout.

Table 5: Correlation between the Teacher Competency and Teacher Burnout

Variables	‘r’ value	Level of significance at 0.01 level
Teacher competency and Teacher Burnout	0.021	Not Significant

It was given in the Table-5. The ‘r’ value was found to be 0.021 which is not significant. Hence, the null hypothesis 5 is accepted. There is no significant relationship between the teacher competency of higher secondary school teachers and their burnout.

Findings of the Study:

- The higher secondary teachers are having average competency.
- The higher secondary teachers are having average burnout.
- The higher secondary teachers do not differ significantly in teacher competency in respect of gender.
- The higher secondary teachers do not differ significantly in teacher competency in respect of educational qualification.
- The higher secondary students do not differ significantly in teacher burnout in respect of gender.
- The higher secondary students differ significantly in teacher burnout in respect of educational qualification.
- There is no significant relationship between the teacher competency of higher secondary school teachers and their burnout.

Conclusion:

In the present study the teacher competency and teacher burnout at higher secondary level. It is revealed that the higher secondary teachers are having average competency and burnout and there is no significant relationship between the teacher competency of higher secondary school teachers and their burnout.

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